

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF FARMERS ON CLIMATE CHANGE AND
ADAPTATION STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE CROP PRODUCTION IN NORTH EAST,
NIGERIA**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14729499>

ABSTRACT

Climate change impacts are felt on agricultural production, health, biodiversity, social and economic conditions, people and environment, hence its importance. This study determined farmers' socio-economic characteristics in North east, Nigeria. The study adopted structured questionnaire which was validated by experts. The population of the study was 382 farmers, with 256 male and 85 female. The instrument was tested for internal consistency and reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. The data were analyzed using Frequency and Percentage. Findings revealed that majority of the farmers (75%) are male while 25% are female; 27% are under 20-30 years of age, and 16% are under 51-60 years, while 4% are 60 year and above. In addition, 20% have less than 5 years farming experience, 14% have 16-20 year, and 10% have more than 20 years of experience. Furthermore, 33% holds SSCE certificate, while 25% have First School Leaving Certificate, 13% have degree and 5% have postgraduate, while 4% have no qualification. The paper recommends that young farmers, and those that have attained O'Level and post-secondary level education should be targeted to create the desired effect with regards to climate change and adaptation strategies for crop production.

Keywords: Adaptation Strategies, Climate Change, Socio-Economic Characteristics, Sustainable Crop Production

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, interest in climate change and adaptation strategies has grown significantly in various parts of the world, Nigeria inclusive. This interest might have been spurred by the adverse effects of climate change which have increased dramatically as flooding have exacerbated, desertification intensified, food shortage increasing, coupled with loss of bio species, among others adverse effects (Mbakwe, Judith, & Obaji, 2015). These imply that climate change is a global phenomenon that has profound implications for agriculture, particularly in developing countries as it poses significant effect on agriculture in the area of food crop production, forestry, fisheries, infrastructure as well as the socioeconomic status of the people.

Previously, Nigeria exported a broad range of primary commodities, including a substantial share of the world's cocoa, palm oil, groundnuts, cotton, hides, skins, rubber, and coffee, as well as coal, tin, and other minerals (World Bank, 2021). Agricultural exports slumped, and oil expanded from an average of 12 percent of total exports in the early 1960s to 95 percent two decades (i.e 20 years) later. In 2020 agricultural output went up by 2.2 percent, slightly below 2019's 2.4 percent

growth. Crop production, which represents 90 percent of total agricultural production, drove the expansion, especially staple foods like rice, corn, beans, and cassava for domestic consumption (Nigeria development update, 2021). Nigeria, a predominantly agricultural country (70% of its population are engaged in farming) with a largely subsistence-based agricultural sector (88.4% are small holders) and a very rapidly growing population (Cervigni et al., 2013; UN, 2022).

Crop production is a branch of agriculture that deals with growing crops for use as food and fiber. It depends on the availability of arable land and is affected in particular by yields, macroeconomic uncertainties, as well as consumption patterns (Agba, Adewara, Adama, Adzer, & Atoyebi, 2017). In the last few decades, farmers have been facing different types of challenges ranging from high temperature, extreme weather events such as floods, drought, pests and diseases, weeds insurgence and fluctuating rainfall, incidence of pest and diseases, low agricultural productivity, alteration of surface and ground water and devastation of eco-system among others (Adebayo, 2010; Agba et al, 2017; Mbakwe, Judith, & Obaji, 2015).

On their part, Myeni and Moeletsi (2020), Agba et al (2017), and Bako (2013), have argued that the agricultural sector and crop production have perhaps been most hard hit by climate change with decline in crop production which has heightened fears of increasing levels of food shortages, famine, and has festered a volatile environment with critical production levels. These meant that a disruption of crop production could exacerbate social tensions, which would further dampen investor enthusiasm and could lead to political instability, and more conflict, and the attendant negative effects such as social and economic crises; domestic violence, which includes physical, emotional and sexual abuse, increase in the number of out of school children, among others (Agba et al, 2017).

Climate change and environmental degradation has also affected communities, businesses and organizations globally, inadvertently impacting the financial markets and the global economy (Tukur, 2015). This translates to farmers experiencing low productivity in crop production and diminishing standard of living. In addition, profound changes to the dynamics of climate change have triggered awareness and perception of its adverse effects, prompting massive investment into adaptation strategies and mitigation efforts, and the accelerated transformation of crop production in some advanced countries (Bartels & Furman, 2016). However, in Nigeria, insecurity is driving internal displacement and crippling the economic activities of vulnerable communities (Mohammed, 2014). Data on poverty for Nigeria indicates that the north east and north west of the country have the highest incidences of conflict events, also have the highest poverty rates (World Bank Report, 2021).

Mbakwe, Judith, and Obaji (2015) evaluated socioeconomic characteristics, trends, perceptions and adaptation options of arable crop farmers to climate change in Imo State, Nigeria and found the mean age of famers to be 43.24 years with the majority (73.33%) males, and greater proportions of them (71.67%) were married with an average household size of six persons; the average farm size was 0.97 hectares. In addition, Mbakwe, Judith, and Obaji (2015) confirmed the evidence of climate change and its negative impact in Imo state, Nigeria as their study revealed a sustained decrease in number of rainy days and relative humidity with temperature levels and sunshine duration showing significant trend. The researchers expressed concerns that if the trend continues, arable crop production (vegetables, maize, okra, roots and tubers) in the area would be adversely affected with time. Furthermore, Mbakwe, Judith, and Obaji (2015) revealed that perceptions of farmers on climatic variables were all in line with the trends result, with the farmers responding to climate change through the adoption of local practices to thwart the negative impacts of climate change. Mbakwe, Judith, and Obaji (2015) concluded that the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers had a significant influence on their adaptation options to climate change.

The resources, efforts and time needed to be expended on climate change and adaptation strategies means that vulnerable farmers (female) are more exposed to the adverse effects of climate change and it is more difficult for them to seek help. This could be attributed to the farmers' socioeconomic characteristics, which include; low level of educational background, lack of access to social amenities and economic opportunities; high rate of poverty, lack of empowerment, impact of traditional/religious beliefs and cultural practices (Mohammed, 2023). In response to increasing concern about awareness and perception of climate change and adaptation strategies for sustainable crop production in the study area, Mohammed, Iliya and Ndomi (2023) developed a theoretical framework on climate change and adaptation strategies for sustainable crop production.

It is important to note that crop production activities rely on operations and inputs such as clearing, tillage, application of manure/fertilizer, pesticides and use of machines and other equipment. These operations which are necessary to achieve the goal of crop production and to meet the food needs of the people in the study area (North east Nigeria) contribute substantial emission of greenhouse gases like Methane (CH₄), Nitrate (N₂O), and Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) to the global stock of Green House Gasses (GHGs) that warms the environment and subsequently lead to climate change. Climate change occurs because of the concentrations of these emitted gases in the atmosphere that cause alteration in a number of factors that in turn affect the productivity of cultivated crops.

The implication is that farmers' bid to produce more food crops in order to meet up with growing population, urbanization, and food needs/requirements through exploitation of land resources, has mainly contributed to climate change problems and climate change in turn leaves negative effects on the ecosystem which in turn affects crop production and yield. These negative effects portend grave danger to crop production, food distribution and retailing, which may come under strain as a result of people panic-buying. These could lead to increase in the prices of food items and agricultural produce; rising concerns about imminent food shortage. Concerns about food running out also meant that vulnerable populations who cannot afford to buy food, and therefore may not find food.

Furthermore, the variations in climate parameters affect different sectors of the economy such as agriculture, health, water resource and energy (Tukur, 2015). Climate change manifest in various parameters including cloud cover, flooding, rainfall, precipitation, temperature ranges from high and low, sea levels and vapor pressure (MOEFRN, 2003). Agriculture contributes to climate change, producing significant effects through the production and release of Green House Gases GHGs). Clearing of forests for agricultural production replaces forest with crops thereby reducing the rate at which carbon dioxide gas trapping and absorbing (Stern, 2014; Chikaire, 2013).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Accordingly, adapting to climate change entails taking the right measures to reduce the negative effects of climate change (or exploit the positive ones) by making the appropriate adjustments and changes (Mohammed, Kwaghe, Bukar, & Umar, 2013; Myeni & Moeletsi, 2020). Adaptation has three possible objectives: to reduce exposure to the risk of damage; develop the capacity to cope with unavoidable damages; and to take advantage of new opportunities (Anyanwu, 2013; Ngigi, 2009). The implication is that adaptation strategies are indispensable to crop production as countries around the world have resorted to a number of adaptation strategies to contain the increasing adverse effects of climate change (Chikaire, 2013; Nnadi, 2014; Zakari, Ibro, Moussa, & Abdoulaye, 2022). In addition, Anyanwu (2013) and Ngigi (2009) have outlined the common adaptation strategies employ by farmers to mitigate/caution/counter the adverse effects of climate change which include, planting of drought resistant varieties of crops, crop diversification, change in cropping pattern and calendar of

planting, climate information and forecasting, cropping adjustment, production management and practices, irrigation efficiency, mixed cropping, irrigation efficiency, crop residues especially maize and guinea corn as well as grasses, and mulching. These imply that suggestions on adaptation strategies on adverse effects of climate change are likely to impact the number of available extension workers, NGOs, and delivery staff critical to ensuring compliance with the adaptation strategies which have profound implications for crop production in general.

In spite of the above manifest importance of adaptation strategies aimed at combating the effects of climate change, preliminary investigations questions whether the socioeconomic characteristics of farmers affect/influence farmers' perception on climate change and adaptation strategies for sustainable crop production (Hassan et al., 2018). In addition, it was also suggested that sufficient attention has not been paid to the socioeconomic characteristics of farmers' perception on climate change and adaptation strategies in the North east, Nigeria (Mohammed, 2023). However, some studies (For instance; Adebayo et al., 2013; Ajayi, 2014) have assessed farmers' climate change awareness, perceptions and adaptation options.

This work therefore shall add to the repository of knowledge on socioeconomic characteristics of farmers' perception on climate change and adaptation strategies in Nigeria, hence, further promoting the practice of mitigating the challenges posed by climate change for optimal and sustainable crop production. It is hoped that the finding of this paper will be useful to farmers in the North east with a view to improving their adaptation strategies for sustainable crop production. The findings and recommendations of the paper will also serve as a reference material for farmers, extension workers, government agencies and NGOs on the importance of considering the socioeconomic characteristics of farmers' perception on climate change and adaptation strategies for crop production in the study area.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to determine the socioeconomics characteristic of farmers in Northeast, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTION

What are the socio-economics characteristics of farmers in North east, Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Farmers socio-economic characteristics are an important factor in climate change and adaptation strategies for sustainable crop production in general, hence, its inclusion in most studies that explored farmers perception and/or awareness on climate change and adaptation strategies for sustainable crop production in both developed and developing countries. For instance, Modibbo, Ali, and Ahmed (2020) analyze the socio-economic, environmental and energy sector of Nigeria, and regarded the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), electricity consumption, employment and greenhouse gases emissions as the key sustainable development goals (SDGs) for the year 2030, upon which all other goals depend on directly or indirectly. The study is broad, considering others factor considered such as environmental and energy sector of Nigeria, in addition to the socio-economic characteristics.

Table 1 shows the North-East Geo-Political zone of Nigeria, which consists of six states, namely: Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe states. In terms of land area, Borno is the largest state with 57,799 sq km followed by Taraba (54, 473 sq km), while Bauchi (49, 119 sq km) is the third in the area but highest in a population of 4,676,465 people. The second most populous state in the North-east is Borno, with 4,171,104 persons. The smallest state in terms of land area is Gombe (18,768 sq km) having the same population as Yobe with 2,321,591 people. Borno state has the highest GDP and

highest number of employments amounting to USD 5175 and 1,396,022 persons, respectively. These could be as a result of the alluvial soil deposited in the Lake Chad basin of the state where the people dwell in fishing and farming activities which create many job opportunities. Taraba is the second state having high employment (877,054 persons) with a GDP of USD 3397 lower than Bauchi and Adamawa but higher than Yobe state. In summary, the landmark of this region is 262,578 square kilometers with a total population of over 18.95 million people, among which over 5.318 million are engaged in different sectors of the economy.

Table 1: North-east states of Nigeria

S//n	State	Area (Km ²)	Population (%)	Employment	GDP (USDM)
1.	Adamawa	36,917	3,168,101 (16.71)	728,744	(13.70)
2.	Bauchi	49,119	4,676,465 (24.67)	634,880	(11.94)
3.	Borno	70,898	4,171,104 (22)	1,396,022	(26.25)
4.	Gombe	18,768	2,321,591 (12.24)	840,037	(15.80)
5.	Taraba	54,473	2,300,736 (12.13)	877,054	(16.49)
6.	Yobe	45,502	2,321,591 (12.24)	841,334	(15.82)

Source: Modibbo, Ali, and Ahmed (2020).

Using random sampling of 378 smallholder farmers and a questionnaire survey for data collection, Asare-Nuamah and Fonteh Amungwa (2021) explored the adaptation strategies of smallholder farmers in Ghana, and analyzed the predictors of effective adaptation. Descriptive and inferential statistics using the SPSS software revealed that smallholder farmers adopt multiple adaptation strategies to reduce the impact of climate change. In addition, marital status, years of farming experience, knowledge of climate change, and education turned out to be significant predictors of adaptation. Furthermore, marital status, weedicide application, change in staple food consumption, and planting of early-maturing crops are good predictors of effective adaptation. Asare-Nuamah and Fonteh Amungwa (2021) recommended the need for farmers to intensify adaptation strategies through agricultural extension programs and interventions to improve rural food security and livelihood, adding that the capacity of farmer organizations and rural institutions (particularly agricultural extension and advisory services) should be strengthened.

Mbakwe, Osita, and Obaji (2016) identified farmers' socio-economic characteristics, their perceptions, climatic trends variables, and barriers to climate change in Imo State, Nigeria by adopting the multi-stage random sampling technique in selection of respondents with a sample size of sixty farming households. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection, while the data analyzed using descriptive statistical tools; trend analysis and multinomial logit regression model. The study revealed that the mean age of farmers was 43.24 years, the majority (i.e 73.33%) were males, and large proportions of the farmers (71.67%) were married with an average household size of six persons, and the average farm size was 0.97 ha. In addition, access to credit, extension services, farming experience, education, access to credit, access to climate change information and farm size were some of the significant determinants of farm-level adaptation options. Mbakwe, Osita, and Obaji (2016) concluded that if a sustained decrease in number of rainy days and relative humidity continued, while the temperature level and sunshine duration increases significantly, arable crop production (vegetables, maize, okra, roots and tubers) in the area may be adversely affected in the long run. This implied that socio-economic characteristics of the farmers have a significant influence on their adaptation options to climate change as farmers complained of inadequate information. The study recommended that agricultural policies and programmes should focus on intensifying awareness on climate change in order to influence farmer's adaptation to climate change positively.

Alhassan, Shaibu, Kuwornu, and Damba (2018) determine the factors influencing farmers' awareness and choice of indigenous adaptation strategies by applying the Heckman Two-Stage Sample Selection Model. Questionnaire was administered to 285 randomly selected households, and the outcome showed that majority of farmers are aware of and employed soil related indigenous adaptation strategies. The study revealed the following as factors that determines farmers' awareness of indigenous adaptation strategies; education, membership of farmer-based organization, farmer-farmer extension contacts and farming experience significantly determine. The study also showed that farmers' level of education, farming experience, farmer-farmer extension contacts, membership of farmer group, labour hours and age significantly influenced farmers' choice of indigenous climate related adaptation strategies. Alhassan, Shaibu, Kuwornu, and Damba (2018) recommended the formation of farmers' groups to serve as a vehicle for sharing knowledge on indigenous farming practices for effective climate change adaptation.

Fahada, Inayatd, Wanga, Dongb, Hub, Khanb, and Khanc (2020) employed a probit model approach to analyze the farm households' awareness of climate change and its associated socioeconomic and demographic variables, and revealed that 73 % farm households were aware of climate change. The study also showed that socio economics and demographic variables such as age of farm households, education level, farming experience, land ownership status, extension and information sources access were related to farm households' awareness of climate change. In addition, the evaluation of farm households' adaptation behavior suggests that farm households are active in using several adaptation strategies such as crop diversification and use of irrigation etc.

In general, the literature review has shown that adaptation is dependent on multiple socioeconomic factors, such as age, gender, years of farming experience, assets, level of education, household size, and technology. It also demonstrated that there are differences and similarities between the various studies reviewed with regards to the socio-economic characteristics of farmers on climate change and adaptation strategies in Nigeria. This implies that farmers' adaptation to climate change is dependent on multiple socioeconomic factors.

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted the survey research design which involves gathering of information about a large number of people or objects by studying a representative sample of the entire group (Bhattarai, 2021; Yalams & Ndomi, 2000). The design is considered appropriate because the study was carried out directly on the farmers; the questionnaires were administered to the farmers. In addition, Survey Research Design permit generalization to be made on wider population even when the study sample is small (Creswell, 2013). The target population comprise of 75,000 farmers from all the household survey of farmers in Northeast Nigeria. Farmers were selected using Multi-stage Sampling technique from the farming communities using the National Indicator for Agricultural Household Survey (NIHHS). The first stage involved the selection two agricultural zones randomly selected in each of the six-state (which made-up North-east Nigeria). This gave rise to twelve agricultural zones. With the help of research assistants, extension services department, Agricultural Development Programme, and farming communities (from each of the twelve agricultural zone), (a list was compiled from which two farming communities each were selected from the twelve agricultural zones, which gave rise to a total of twenty-four communities. Using Krejcie and Morgan's table for determining sample size, a sample size of 382 farmers was determined (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970), cited in Gamaraja (2021). It should be noted that the sample size of 382 farmers was based on the fact that

382 sample holds the statistical power to represent a population of 75,000 as posited by (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970), cited in Gamaraja (2021).

Structured questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The questionnaire sought information on the respondents' (i.e farmers) biographic data / information such as age, gender, years of farming experience and number and size of farm land. This study relied on the opinions of farmers (respondents) on climate change and adaptation strategies for crop production in the study area. The summary of the demographic information of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

RESULTS

Based on the research question raised; What are the socio-economics characteristics of farmers in North east, Nigeria. The results revealed that majority of the farmers, 256 (75.07%) are male while the remaining 85 (24.93%) are female. The result reveals that 91 (26.69%) are under ages 20-30 year of age, 65 (19.06%) are under ages 31-40 year, 118 (34.60%) of the farmers are under age 41-50 years, 53 (15.54%) are under the ages of 51-60 years while 14 (4.11%) are 60 year and above.

Table 2: Frequency Counts and Percentages of the Socio-economic Characteristics of the Farmers in the Study Area

S/N	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender		
	Male	256	75.07
	Female	85	24.93
2	Farmers Age		
	20-30 years	91	26.69
	31-40 years	65	19.06
	41-50 years	118	34.60
	51-60 years	53	15.54
3	Above 60 years	14	4.11
	Years of Experience into Farming		
	Below 5 years	69	20.23
	6-10years	127	37.24
	11-15years	64	18.77
	16-20 years	47	13.78
4	Above 20 years	34	9.98
	Farm Size		
	Below 1 Ha	100	29.33
	1- 5 Ha	141	41.35
	6-10 Ha	66	19.35
	11-15 Ha	14	4.11
5	16 Ha above	20	5.86
	Educational Level		
	PSLC	87	25.51
	SSCE	113	33.14
	NCE	68	19.94
	Degree	43	12.61
6	Postgraduate	18	5.28
	None	12	3.52
	Income Status of the Farmers		
	High income earners	57	16.72
	Middle income earners	218	63.93
	Low-income earners	66	19.35

The results also reveal that 69 (20.23%) have below 5 years of experience into farming, 127 (37.24%) have 6 – 10 years of experience, 64 (18.77%) have 11 – 15 years of experience, 47(13.78%) have 16-20 year of experience and 34 (9.98%) have more than 20 years of experience. The results also revealed that majority of the farmers, 113 (33.14%) holds SSCE certificate. The result also reveals that 87(25.51%) of the farmers have First School Leaving Certificate, 68 (19.94%) have OND, NCE/HND, 43 (12.61%) have degree and 18 (5.28%) have postgraduate while 12 (3.52%) have no qualification (None). Furthermore, about 57 (16.72%) of the farmers are high income earners, 218 (63.93%) are middle income earners, 66 (19.35%) are low-income earners respectively. In view of the foregoing and considering the detailed background of the respondents in terms of their socio-economic characteristics, the respondents can be considered to have reasonable knowledge on climate change and adaptation strategies for crop production in the study area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings arising from the socio-economic characteristics of farmers in the study area on Table 2 implies that adaptation strategies in the area may not come as easy as may be expected on the simple reason that greater percentage of the farmers are engaged in subsistence mode of production which is in contrast to commercially oriented production. This finding is consistent with report of Food and Agricultural Organisation (2019). FAO stated that the country's agricultural sector is heterogeneous, comprising small through medium to large scale farmers and farms with different levels of efficiency. Smallholders (subsistence mode of production), however, dominate the agricultural and livestock production landscape. The report further states that agricultural crop production is constrained by a variety of institutional and socioeconomic bottlenecks. Some of the socioeconomic factors which affects technology adoption is the mode of production, level of education and farmers farm size and income.

Findings arising from the socio-economic characteristics of farmers is supported by the work of Keelan et al. (2010) who showed that farmer's education, age, gender, and household size have influence on decision to adopt new technology. These findings were further supported by Ajewole (2010) who found that, education level of farmers, years spent to access formal education, household size and off farm income positively influences the adoption decisions, while farming experience, farm/herd size, and distance from source of supply of new technology have negative influenced on it.

CONCLUSION

The study has revealed that the number of farmers [i.e majority of farmers; $91+65= 156$ (47%)] with an average age of between the ages of 18 - 25, and ages 30 - 45, and with qualifications ranging from holders of O' Level, first degree, and PhDs, coupled with possessing over 20 years farming experience meant that if properly trained and guided on adaptation strategies, the farmers could achieve high yield in term of crop production in view of their qualifications and farming experience, in spite of the adverse effects of climate change in the study area. In addition, the high percentage of middle-income earners among the farmers (63.93%) suggests the lucrative nature of engagement in crop production. Furthermore, the difference between the ratio of high-income earners (16.72%) and low-income earners (19.35%) among the farmers is a pointer to the need for collaboration between them so as to achieve high yield and self-sufficiency in crop production in the study area.

In addition, the study has also pointed to the need for medium- and longer-term planning in order to achieve sustainable crop production following the crisis originated by climate change and (compounded by Boko Haram insurgency in parts of the study area). In other words, a broad socioeconomic development plan is also needed so that those young male and female farmers (aged between 18 and 25 years, and those between 30 and 45 years old respectively) can continue with robust and sustainable crop production and derive the benefit there from in site of the challenges of climate change.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on observations and findings of the study:

1. Efforts should be geared towards implementing adult education targeting young but uneducated farmers, in view of their socio-economic characteristics, and the sampled age group that are educated (O'Level and post-secondary level education) to create the desired effect in terms of resilience to climate change.
2. The farmers should be encouraged to adapt their local knowledge of climate change and adaptation strategies to modern adaptation practices/strategies in countering the adverse impacts of climate change in the study area. However, this should not be at the expense of modern scientific knowledge.
3. Farmers should be assisted with agricultural inputs and access to affordable credit to enable farmers attains flexibility to change strategies in crop production in response to adverse effects of climate change in the study area.

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